

Short Distances Enable Walking Even for Car-Owning Families with Children: Implications for the X-Minute City

Zahra Mahabadi*, Ana Basiri*¹

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Summary

This study examines the relationship between short-distance travel and walking among car-owning households with children in the UK. Using data from the National Travel Survey, the analysis focuses on home-based trips for everyday activities. The results show a strong and consistent association between shorter travel distances and walking, even among households typically considered car-dependent. This relationship holds across different levels of neighbourhood deprivation and urban-rural contexts. Spatial differences are modest, with most variation occurring at the household and trip level. The findings support planning approaches that reduce everyday travel distances to encourage walking.

KEYWORDS: Short-distance travel, Walking behaviour, Car-owning households, X-minute city

1. Introduction

Walking is widely recognised as an important mode of travel due to its benefits for public health, environmental sustainability, and urban liveability. However, walking behaviour varies substantially across population groups and spatial contexts. Previous research consistently shows that car ownership is associated with lower levels of walking (Ghimire & Bardaka, 2023), and that families with children are among the most structurally car-dependent groups (Carver et al., 2013). Walking behaviour is also shaped by neighbourhood characteristics. Studies have shown that walking is more common in urban areas than in rural settings (Hutchinson, White, & Graham, 2014), while deprived areas often exhibit lower levels of walking, particularly for short everyday trips (Burns et al., 2022). Together, these findings suggest that households with children, access to a car, and residence in deprived or less urban areas face multiple constraints on walking. At the same time, a growing body of planning research emphasises the importance of short travel distances for supporting walking (McCarthy et al., 2017), as reflected in concepts such as the X-minute city (Moreno, C. et al. 2021). Despite this, little empirical research has examined whether households that are typically considered car-dependent are willing to walk when everyday trips are short. This study addresses this gap by examining the association between short-distance trips and walking among car-owning households with children, and by assessing how this relationship differs across levels of neighbourhood deprivation and urban-rural context.

2. Methodology

The analysis is based on data from the UK National Travel Survey covering the period from 2002 to 2019, prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. The study focuses on households that own at least one car and include at least one child younger than 15 years old. By focusing on these households, the study examines whether households that have access to a car and face potential limitations on walking due to the presence of children remain walking-oriented on average. The analysis focuses on the distance and mode of home-based trips, chaining from home to food shopping, non-food shopping, service, social,

¹ School of Geographical and Earth Sciences, University of Glasgow

and entertainment purposes. This restriction is applied because the study is motivated by the concept of the X-minute city, which emphasises access to everyday activities from home within short distances.

Within this context, the main question is to what extent household walking behaviour is associated with the concentration of short-distance trips. In other words, whether car-owning households with children walk more when a larger share of their trips are made over short distances, which would be consistent with the idea of the X-minute city. To address this question, household-level generalised linear models are estimated to relate walking behaviour to trip distance composition, number of trips, trip chaining, and trip purpose.

2.1. Household-Level Model Specification and Robustness Checks

All models are estimated within a binomial logit framework (Equation 1) at the household level. This specification is implemented in three related ways. First, a fractional logit model is estimated in which the dependent variable is the household walking share, defined as the proportion of trips made on foot, and observations are weighted by the total number of household trips. Second, as a robustness check, a binomial count model is estimated in which the number of walking trips is modelled as successes out of total household trips, with total trip volume included as a control. This approach allows an assessment of whether the results are sensitive to the way walking behaviour is measured. In all models, heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors are used.

As an additional robustness check, a binomial model is estimated to verify that the association between short-trip share and walking is not mechanically driven by differences in total trip-making across households. In this model, the number of walking trips is modelled as a function of the share of short-distance trips, with the total number of household trips held fixed. Under this specification, changes in the short-trip share reflect the replacement of longer trips with shorter trips within a fixed number of household trips. Under this specification, the coefficient on the short-trip share captures the association between walking probability and the replacement of longer trips with shorter trips within a household's travel portfolio.

Equation 1: Binomial logit specification for household walking trips

$$W_h \sim \text{Binomial}(T_h, p_h) \quad \text{Logit}(p_h) = X_h\beta$$

where:

- W_h is the number of walking trips made by household h ,
- T_h is the total number of trips made by household h ,
- p_h is the probability that a trip is made on foot.

2.2. Social and Spatial Heterogeneity in Walking Responses

As a complementary analysis, trip-level binomial logit models are estimated to test whether the short-trip-walking relationship varies across social and spatial contexts. The dependent variable is a binary indicator of walking for each trip, and the key explanatory variable is a short-trip indicator. Moderation is tested by interacting the short-trip indicator with (i) neighbourhood deprivation measured using the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) and (ii) urban-rural residential context based on Primary Sampling Unit (PSU) area types (grouped into ordered categories from rural to inner metropolitan). Because multiple trips are observed per household, standard errors are clustered by HouseholdID in the trip-level models. To examine whether the association between short-trip availability and walking differs by household composition, a pooled multilevel binomial logit model is estimated combining households with and without children. The model includes an interaction between short-trip share and a binary indicator for households with children, with random intercepts and random slopes for short-trip share at the local authority level to capture spatial heterogeneity.

3. Result

Across all models and specifications, households with a higher share of short-distance trips exhibit higher levels of walking. In the fractional logit model, a 10 percentage-point increase in the short-trip share is associated with an average increase of 2.8 percentage points in the predicted walking share ($p < 0.001$).

Table 1: Household-level regression results for walking behaviour

Variables	Fractional logit (Walking share)	Binomial GLM (Walking trip ratio)	Binomial GLM (Trips held fixed)
Short-trip	2.433*** (share)	0.093*** (count)	2.460*** (share)
Average chain length	-0.155***	-0.146***	-0.188***
Short × chain interaction	-0.204**	-0.010**	-0.2009**
Total trips	-0.008***	-0.051***	-
Non-food shopping	0.451***	0.229*	0.378***
Service	-0.336**	-0.407***	-0.436***
Social	0.281**	0.082*	0.170*
Entertainment	1.365***	1.180***	1.250***
Constant	-3.210***	-1.919***	-3.296***
Pseudo R ² (CS)	0.633	0.575	0.629

*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

Average trip chain length is negatively associated with walking, and the interaction between short-trip share and chain length is also negative. However, the estimated effects indicate that the association between short-distance trips and walking remains positive across the observed range of chain lengths. The negative coefficient on total trips suggests that households making more trips tend to have a lower walking share, but the positive association between short-distance trips and walking persists after controlling for overall trip volume. Trip-purpose composition also matters for walking behaviour. Relative to food shopping, walking is more prevalent in households with a higher share of entertainment, social, and non-food shopping trips, and less prevalent in households with a higher share of service-oriented trips. The results are robust to an alternative binomial count specification modelling walking trips out of total trips, as well as to a specification holding total trips fixed. In both cases, short-distance trips remain positively associated with walking, indicating that the results are not driven by differences in overall trip-making across households.

Trip-level moderation models further show that short-distance trips are substantially more likely to be walked than longer trips across all social and spatial contexts. Neighbourhood deprivation has a statistically significant but modest moderating effect: while households in more deprived areas walk less overall, the increase in walking associated with short-distance trips is slightly larger in more deprived neighbourhoods. Average marginal effects indicate that converting a longer trip into a short trip increases the probability of walking by approximately 31 percentage points in the most deprived areas and 26 percentage points in the least deprived areas. Similarly, the association between short-distance trips and walking varies across urban-rural contexts. Interaction terms with PSU area types are jointly statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 75.38$, $p < 0.001$). Average marginal effects show that short-distance trips increase the probability of walking in all area types, with the largest effects observed in inner metropolitan (approximately 36 percentage points) and rural areas (approximately 34 percentage points), and smaller but still substantial effects in small and large urban areas. Overall, these findings indicate that shorter travel distances strongly encourage walking across all contexts, although the magnitude of this effect varies by household constraints, neighbourhood deprivation, and urban form.

LAUA-specific marginal effect of +10pp short-trip share on walking (Δpp)

Figure 1: Spatial heterogeneity in the walk-enabling effect of short trips

Multilevel models indicate that only a small share of variation in walking is attributable to local authority context, with an intraclass correlation below 2%. Consistent with this, mapped residuals in Figure 1 show only modest and spatially unsystematic local deviations. While the effect of short-distance travel varies slightly across local authorities, this heterogeneity is not explained by neighbourhood deprivation or urban-rural classification. Overall, the walking response to short-distance trips appears broadly consistent across places. In addition, the pooled multilevel model indicates a strong positive association between short-trip share and walking. Households with children have lower baseline walking, but a stronger positive interaction in log-odds terms. However, as shown in Figure 2, predicted probabilities indicate that they remain less likely to walk across the observed range, with the gap widening as short-trip share increases. Substantial variation is observed across local authority areas.

Figure 2: Predicated walking probability by household type

4. Discussion and conclusion

This study examines walking behaviour among car-owning households with children, a group often considered highly car-dependent. The results show a strong and consistent association between short-distance trips and walking, even after controlling for trip volume, trip chaining, and trip purpose composition. Households with a higher concentration of short trips are more likely to walk. This relationship holds across different social and spatial contexts. Short-distance trips are associated with higher walking probabilities not only in inner metropolitan areas, but also in rural and more deprived areas, where walking is often assumed to be less feasible. Although walking levels are lower on average in these contexts, households are more likely to switch from car use to walking when trips are short. Overall, the findings indicate that travel distance remains a key constraint on walking, even for households with access to a car and childcare responsibilities. By showing that shorter everyday trips are linked to more active travel across a wide range of contexts, the results support planning approaches such as the X-minute city and suggest potential benefits for public health and environmental sustainability.

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Biographies

Dr. Zahra Mahabadi is a Research Associate in Urban Analytics, using data-driven methods to study mobility, urban form, and equitable planning. Prof. Ana Basiri is Professor of Geospatial Data Science at the University of Glasgow, focusing on bias and missingness in spatial data. She is a UKRI Future Leaders Fellow and Editor-in-Chief of *Journal of Navigation*.